

PART II: PHOSPHORYLATED SOL-GEL FLAME RETARDANT COATING FOR POLYESTER FABRIC

A. A. Younis^{1*}, M. A. Nour¹ and Kh. El-Nagar²

¹Fire and Explosion Protection (FEP), National Institute for Standards (NIS), Giza, Egypt.

²Textile Metrology Lab (TML), National Institute for Standards (NIS), Giza, Egypt.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Ahmed A. Younis (Email: dr_ahmedabdee@yahoo.com)

Keywords: Polyester, UL/94, LOI, Sol-gel, Thermal decomposition

Abstract

This research was built to investigate the main role of phosphorylated sol-gel (PSG) to reduce the ignition problems of polyester fabric. Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA), Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) of the un-treated and treated samples were investigated. PSG material was played as protective shielding coat and improved the thermal behavior. FTIR analysis of the treated sample showed that there is a sort of interaction between the molecules of PSG and the fabric. Limiting oxygen index (LOI) for the lowest oxygen concentration needed to start the ignition showed also an improvement in the ignition retarding behavior due to this treatment. To increase the affinity of fibers towards PSG, the fabric surface was exposed to UV/Ozone for different periods. Exposing samples for 90 min showed the best results comparing to other samples (irradiated for UV/Ozone for 0, 30 and 125 min). Ignition behavior (UL/94) was also applied on samples by using flame chamber for determination the rate of burning. The results of UL/94 (according to Standard 1210) confirmed the ignition behavior results produced from LOI.

1. Introduction

Polyester is a synthetic fabric, which is made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) polymers. These polymers are composed of at least 85% by weight of ester, dihydric alcohol and terephthalic acid. There are two types of polyester; saturated and unsaturated ones. The first type can be defined as that the polyester which the backbones are saturated and hence non-reactive as compared to the more reactive, unsaturated ones. On other hand, unsaturated polyester is consisting of alkyl thermo-setting resins characterized by vinyl unsaturated. Synthetic fibers surpass the production of natural fibers with more than 55% of products in the textile industry [1]. It can be used in two ways; as a raw material by itself or as a blend because of its wrinkle its wrinkle-resistant property and its ability to retain its shape [2]. PET has several application in industries as; electronic materials, automobile

industries, packaging and household [3, 4]. PET fiber has major advantages of high modulus and strength, quick drying, hardness, resistant to biological damage such as mold and mildew, stretch, wrinkle and abrasion resistances, relatively low cost, and easy recycling [4, 5]. Besides many beneficial properties, synthetic fibers show various disadvantages such as is highly flammable, low dyeability, less wearing comfort, difficulties in finishing and insufficient washability associated with their hydrophobic nature [5, 6]. This research aimed to activate the PET fabric surface in order to produce free radicals to react with PSG [7]. For this purpose, many great studies have been carried out including, thermal analysis (TGA and DSC), which play an important role to study the flame-retardant of polyester. It supplies important information for the evaluation and the development of flame-retardant polyester via the profile of their thermal decomposition [8-11]. This indicate that, the sample irradiate to UV/Ozone for 90 min has the best results as fire-retardant than the other. Secondly, the samples are exposed to flammability tests as; LOI and UL/94. The Fourier transform infrared is used to determine the peaks which appeared and disappeared in all samples. Also, the results of the optical properties such as; whiteness, yellowness and weight loss tests were followed.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

The following fabric was used throughout this study: Mill-scoured and bleached plane 1/1 weaved duck polyester fabric of 140 g/m² weight. It was provided by Misr company for spinning and weaving, El-Mahala El-Kobra, Egypt. There are two kinds of this fabric; un-treated and treated samples with phosphorylated sol-gel coating as mentioned in part I [12].

2.2. Ultraviolet-Ozone Treatment

The studied Polyester fabric (100%) samples firstly were exposed to UV/Ozone [13] for different irradiation periods ranging from 30 min to 125 min then immersed in the freshly prepared sol-gel solution for

two minutes and finally padded under constant pressure for 100% uptake. The treated samples dried in furnace at 140°C for four minutes [11].

2.3. Weight of Polyester Fabric

Five samples were cut to specific area and weighed by Mettler Toledo of accuracy (0.1 mg). The weight was calculated for the square meter [14].

2.4. Colour Measurements

Colour parameters for all examined samples were determined using colour Eye @ 3100 spectrophotometer SDL England in accordance with standard test method [15, 16]. The instrument was used to measure the colour parameters, e.g., L (lightness), a (red-green), b (yellow-blue), W (whiteness) and Y (yellowness) colour components in accordance with the CIE-Lab colour measuring system [17, 18].

2.5. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR of 100% PET fabric samples (treated and untreated) were recorded by means of Nicolet 380 Spectrometer – USA that is equipped with zinc selenide crystal, in the wavelength range 4000–400 cm^{-1} . To ensure reproducible contact between the crystal face and the fabric, a pressure of about 18 Kpa [19] is applied to the crystal holder. The FTIR absorbents frequencies for the treated samples are recorded with an average of 32 scans using a resolution of four cm^{-1} .

2.6. Limiting Oxygen Index (LOI)

The lower concentration of oxygen require to sample ignition was measured by using a Rheometric limiting oxygen index instrument according to standard oxygen index test ISO 4589 [20]. Both nitrogen and oxygen were connected to the apparatus through pressure regulators (see Fig. 1). Determined N_2/O_2 atmospheres were continuously sent through the glass chamber. Samples test were cut in dimension 150 * 50 mm^2 , and then clamped in the holder vertically in the center of the combustion column. The top of the sample was ignited using a propane gas burner. Three or four replicates were tested for each sample to obtain the average LOI value.

2.7. Flame Chamber (UL/94)

The fire-flammability of the samples was evaluated with the UL/94 [21]. This test consists of holding horizontal one of the ends of the sample and maintaining the other extremity in contact with the flame of a Bunsen burner for 30 s (Fig. 2). After the exposed period, the Bunsen burner is removed and the self-extinguish time is measured.

2.8. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

It is an essential laboratory tool which used to determine the mass changes of a sample during thermal decomposition [22, 23]. This TGA can be applied in many fields as; scientific research, petrochemical application, pharmaceutical, and food. The thermal stability of composites was studied using Thermal Analyzer, TGA-50 Shimadzu Instrument-Japan. The analysis is performed under N_2 gas (flow rate: 30 ml/min) at a heating rate of 10°C/min from ambient temperature to 750°C. The weight of tested sample was 6.2 mg that was placed in open platinum pans in the instrument.

2.9. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) [24]

It is used to provide information about thermal changes that do not involve a change in sample mass, characterize the thermophysical properties of polymers as; melting temperature (T_m), heat of melting, percent crystallinity (ΔH_m), glass transition (T_g). This test was performed with DSC-50 Shimadzu Instrument - Japan. The heating rate was 10°C/min and the nitrogen gas was used as; a carrier gas and at a flow rate of 30 ml/min. Samples were repeated three times to insure repeatability. Scans are started at temperature 30°C to a final temperature of 650°C.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Weight Loss of Polyester Fabric

Figure 3 shows the effect of irradiation with UV/Ozone on weight sample (g/m^2). The data showed that the sample weights were decreased with the increasing of time for all studied range (0 to 125 min). Weight loss was affected by irradiating up to 90 min followed by insignificant decrement for extended irradiation time due to dry and photo-oxidation actions [25]. The changes in Figure 3 could be returned to the combined effect of UV and Ozone on the PET. Ozone action is always based on the effect of direct and indirect reactions with PET fibers. This is consequential to the disintegration of ozone ($\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{O}_2 + \text{O}$); oxygen free radical reacts with the water content producing OH-radicals and/or primary and secondary hydroxyl groups (R-OH) on the cellulosic fibers. These radicals are very short-living compounds that have an even stronger oxidation mechanism than that of ozone [26].

A good oxidative efficiency can be achieved by the coupling of UV radiation and ozone. UV/ozone treatment was essentially a photosensitized oxidation process in which surface molecules are excited and/or dissociated by the absorption of short-wavelength UV radiation. Generally when a polymer is exposed to radiant energy, physical and

chemical changes may occur [27]. It is known that ozone is an excellent oxidizing agent for cellulosic, wool, and silk fabrics [28]. The possible interaction of UV in presence of oxygen on the polymeric materials to produce many free radicals (P^{\cdot} , POO^{\cdot} , HOO^{\cdot} , H^{\cdot} and HO^{\cdot}) explained in Figure 4. These free radicals on the polyester substrate were the responsible active sites for the attachment of treatment sole-gel to the PET substrate. These results are due to the action of UV/Ozone on the PET fabric due to the effect of irradiation in reducing elasticity and decreasing the average molecular chain of the treated fabrics, which may be due to the result of photo-oxidation [31]. These irradiated fibers reacted with phosphorylated sole-gel by either coating and/or cross linking due to the formed radicals resulted from the photo-chemical action of UV/Ozone.

3.2. Determination of the Colour

Results in Table 1 show the effect of irradiation on the colour parameters; L, a, b, W and Y in accordance with the CIE-Lab colour measuring system [17, 18]. Lightness of the PET samples slightly decreased with increasing the exposure time due to the photo-oxidation of the fabric surface. Red-Green component 'a' goes to green side because all results have a negative values and the greenish colour of the samples increased with irradiation up to 90 minutes followed by decreasing with extended time. The same tendency was found for the colour component 'b' that goes to blue colour because all results have positive values [32]. The change in yellowness and whiteness indices can be considered as; a sensitive indication of surface modification for the PET fabric under test during the different treatments. It is also clear from data in Table 1 that, the yellowness value of AS-3P samples is higher than that of unexposed one to UV/Ozone and tends to increase with increasing irradiation time. This may be return to partially photo oxidation of UV/Ozone on sample's surface.

3.3. Infrared Spectroscopy

The FTIR spectroscopic analysis is used to identify and study chemicals composition for uncoated and coated samples with phosphorylated sol-gel after irradiating to UV/Ozone for different periods (30, 90 and 125 minutes) and the infrared of samples was showed in Figure 5. The main structure of the polyester fabric is ester, alcohol, anhydride, aromatic ring and heterocyclic aromatic rings. Alcohol was able to react with anhydride and produce ester groups [33]. That was the reason there was still alcohol and anhydride as; a residual reactants left in the polyester. The carboxyl, ester,

anhydride and alcohol groups showed the polyester fabric was pure PET. It is clear from this Figure that, all samples of polyester exhibits broad band near $3425-3435\text{cm}^{-1}$ due to the OH-stretching vibration of free and hydrogen bonded groups (most probably due to the humidity absorbed by KBr during the preparation of the pellets) [34, 35]. The CH_2 anti-symmetric stretching is appear at $2960-2980\text{cm}^{-1}$. The ester functional groups appeared at $1708-1720\text{cm}^{-1}$, $1260-1280\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $1090-1130\text{cm}^{-1}$, while the aromatic ring observed at $2960-2975\text{cm}^{-1}$, $1575-1585\text{cm}^{-1}$, $1500-1510\text{cm}^{-1}$, $1000-1020\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $720-730\text{cm}^{-1}$. Bands assigned for ethylene CH_2 group of $-\text{O}-(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2)-\text{O}-$ moiety are also observed at $1450-1465\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $840-855\text{cm}^{-1}$. The peak at 1410cm^{-1} corresponded to C-C stretching vibration of the benzene ring which was a stable group.

It was the characteristic absorption peak of PET. The presence of ester groups at 1709 and 1268cm^{-1} which preferred to break under certain conditions. In case of spectra (AS 2P-4P), the characteristic peaks of the sol-gel materials including the O-H stretching bands at $3500-3300\text{cm}^{-1}$. The band at $1630-1650\text{cm}^{-1}$ arose from the H-O-H bending of the absorbed water in case of coated samples only. Si- CH_3 bands give rise to a symmetric CH_3 bending band in the $1230-1245\text{cm}^{-1}$ range. At $1030-1045\text{cm}^{-1}$ the strong band of siloxane (Si-O-Si) is appeared. Phosphorylated coated materials (AS-2P to 4P) spectra show P-OH groups as; two broad bands in the $1030-1045\text{cm}^{-1}$ region. P=O group is present as a strong band near 1250cm^{-1} . The characteristic absorption band of silanol groups (Si-OH) formed during the hydrolysis of the alkoxy groups in methyltrimethoxysilane (MTMS) could be enclosed in this band beside other OH groups. Given that the other characteristic band for Si-OH groups at 950cm^{-1} frequently appeared as; a shoulder, we presume that the poly-condensation reaction occurred to a very high degree [36].

In general when we are comparing the four spectrums of un-treated and treated samples we find the O-H stretching at $3425-3435\text{cm}^{-1}$ increased by UV/Ozone radiation and sol-gel coated samples because the phosphorylated sol-gel materials are rich with such groups, these band intensity decreased with increasing the exposure time due to partial drying and oxidation of the treated samples. C=O stretching band at $1708-1720\text{cm}^{-1}$ decreased due to treatment because most of phosphorylated sol-gel is attached to it.

3.4. Flammability Test

The flammability results are summarized in Table 2. Untreated polyester fabric is a flammable polymer as; shown by the LOI of 18.0%. It achieved class-3

classification in the UL/94 test. Irradiation the sample AS-2P to UV/Ozone for 30 minutes increased the LOI to 24.0% and improved the UL/94 rating to class-1 classification. The LOI of AS-3P was more than doubled when coated with phosphorylated sol-gel after irradiating for 90 min and the best UL/94 (class-1, RB = 0 mm/min) classification was obtained. Therefore, LOI and UL/94 show that AS-3P is flame-retarded well AS-3P is not as flammable as un-treated one (AS-1P) by far. It showed a high LOI (22.0% instead of 18.0%) and reached class-1 classification in UL/94.

3.5. Thermal analyses

3.5.1 Thermogravimetric analysis

Thermogravimetry (TG) provided quantitative information on the weight change process. The amount of char residue formed in thermal degradation of a polymer is a measure of its flame resistance. The amount of final residue provides quantitative information about the flame-retardants activity. Figure 6 shows TGA curves for coated (AS 2P-4P) and uncoated (AS-1P) samples after irradiating to UV/Ozone for different periods. It is illustrated that the AS-1P exhibit weight loss in three steps. The initial stage is observed up to 355.1°C and includes no sample loss. Up to 486°C the second step occurs.

The mass loss in this stage is due to thermal decomposition into CO and carbonaceous char [37, 38] whereas the third weight loss (486-750°C) dehydration and charring reactions tend to be completed with lower thermal stability. It can be seen from Figure 6 that, the coated samples (AS 2P-4P), display weight loss in three steps as well. First step is nearly up to 331°C (0.3% in case of AS-2P, 10.3% in case of AS-3P and 9.7% in case of AS-4P). In case of second step, the second temperature range, actually exhibited one distinctive mass loss peak between 331-520°C.

Mass loss in all coated samples may be explained as follows: Thermal degradation of phosphorylated sol-gel coating begins at a temperature well below that required for thermal degradation of polyester. Thus the coating acts as initial source of ignition in treated polyester samples. Therefore, in second step, the mass loss is mainly due to complete decomposition of the protective coating and partial decomposition of polyester.

At the third weight loss (520-750°C) the dehydration and charring reactions tend to be completed and the weight loss is 72% (AS-2P), 67% (AS-3P) and 69% (AS-4P). This Figure and weight loss percent indicates that AS-3P sample has more char (residue) than other samples because it is more bonded with the polyester layer than other coating,

which plays an important role in protection of polyester from ignition as sacrificial layer, so it is indicative of an effective flame-retardant action.

3.5.2 Differential scanning calorimetry

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) traces for un-treated (AS-1P) and treated (AS 2P-4P) samples with UV/Ozone for different periods are shown in Figure 7. Table 3 indicates the values of the glass-transition temperature (T_g) and the melting temperature (T_m) of all the components of the samples. This data illustrate that, the T_g values is started to increase in direction of coated samples until record the highest value (103.35°C) in case of sample irradiated with UV/Ozone for 90 min, and then started to decrease (90.76°C) in case of AS-4P which irradiated for 125 min. On other hand, the T_m is affected by irradiating periods with UV/Ozone. It is clear from Table 3 that a maximum increasing in T_m was achieved in case of AS-3P. The melting temperature of the coated samples ($T_{m,c}$) is considered the higher value in case of AS-4P than other coated samples, while in case of uncoated sample it has disappeared. These results were supported by oxygen index and UL/94 either. The difference in the shape and area under the peak was noticed in Figure 7 as well. Firstly, the effect of UV/Ozone on the polyester samples thermal stability was observed as endotherm at the range of 123-126°C, since the broader endotherm was formed in both of coated samples after treating with UV/Ozone for different periods. It is clear that, the area under the peak was decreased in case of AS-3P and became more sharply than that of the other coated samples. In case of un-treated sample, a broader endotherm appeared at 260°C, which decrease toward AS-4P to form a sharp one than other coated samples. This variation in shape was attributed to the different degrees of crystallinity found in the samples with different irradiation periods of UV/Ozone treatment. The curve of un-treated sample (AS-1P) at 399°C illustrated the presence of an exothermic peak, which disappeared in case of the treated samples (AS-2P to 4P).

At 440°C observed change in endothermic area, the area became larger and broader at AS-4P sample. This may have indicated the existence of PSG coating with polyester fabric. It is clear that heat flow changed as the samples exposed to UV/Ozone for different periods. These changes were attributed to a variation in crystallization, and are shown in Table 3. Finally, there is a new peak with broader exotherm found in all treated samples except untreated one at 612°C. The highest area under the peak was recorded in case of AS-3P and started to decrease in case of sample AS-2P then AS-4P. This

new peak can be used to approve the decomposition of the residual components of the samples.

4. Conclusions

Thermal characterization gave a fairly good idea of the changes taking place in the PET polymer. The variation in shape and area of endothermic and exothermic peaks indicated changes in T_g , T_m and $T_{m,c}$ regions.

5. Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank Prof. Dr. N. A. El-Zaher (National Institute for Standards) and Ass. Prof. Dr. Badr E. Higazzi (Environmental & Sanitary Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Banha University) for their help and sincere encouragement.

6. Reference

- [1] M. Lewin (ed.). Handbook of Fiber Chemistry. "International Fiber Science and Technology". pp 811-974, 2007.
- [2] <http://schwartz.eng.auburn.edu/polyester/uses.html> (accessed on 16/9/2012).
- [3] M.F. Doherty and J.P. Knapp "Distillation, Azeotropic and Extractive" Kirk-Othmer Concise Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology, 4th edition, John Wiley, NY, pp 635-636, 1999.
- [4] F. Fourne "Synthetic Fibers, Machines and Equipment Manufacture, Properties". Hanser Publishers, Munich, 1999.
- [5] M. Elices and J. Llorca, Fiber Fracture, Elsevier Science Ltd., Oxford, 2002.
- [6] M.M. Badrul Hasan, A. Calvimontes and V. Dutschk "Correlation Between Wettability and Cleanability of Polyester Fabrics Modified by a Soil Release Polymer and Their Topographic Structure". *J. Surfact. Deterg.* Vol. 12(4): 285-294, 2009.
- [7] A.A. Younis, Kh. El-Nagar and M. A. Nour "Characterization of Flammability Behavior of Polyester Fabric Modified with Sol-Gel Technique". Sharm Elshikh-Elmansoura, 11-15/03/2013.
- [8] M. Jaffe "Fibers", Thermal Characterization of Polymeric Materials, E.A. Turi, Ed.; Academic Press: Orlando, pp731-750, 1981.
- [9] I.N. Einhorn, Reprint from Research Abstracts and Reviews, Vol. 13, National Academy of sciences, Washington, DC, 1971, pp 3.
- [10] H.G. Nadeau "Fire Property Data of Cellular Plastics". Technomic Publishing Company, Westport, 1980.
- [11] V.J. Fernandes and A.S. Araujo "Kinetic-Study of H-Y Zeolite Regeneration by Thermogravimetry". *Thermochimica Acta.* Vol. 255: 273-280, 1995.
- [12] A.A. Younis, K. El-Nagar and M.A. Nour "Part I: Characterization of Flammability Behavior of Polyester Fabric Modified with Sol-Gel Technique". *International Journal of Chemistry.* Vol. 5(2):38-46, 2013.
- [13] J. Shao, C.J. Hawkyard and C.M. Carr. Department of Textiles, UMIST, Manchester, UK, *J. of Social Dyers & Colorist*, Vol. 113(4), 1997.
- [14] Kh. El-Nagar, N. Nagy and M. Elgamal "Medical Dressing Treated with Honey/Chitosan Microencapsules". *International Journal of Chemistry.* Vol. 4(2):79-89, 2012.
- [15] ATCC, Standard Method "Colour Measurement, Principles and the Textile Industry". Research Triangle Park in North Carolina from October 24-25, 1991.
- [16] S.S. Wang and L.Y. Shy "Molecular Simulation of Diffusion of Water Molecules in Amorphous Polymer". Proceedings of the 16th Roc. Polymer Symposium. 249-253, 1993.
- [17] Kh. El-Nagar, M.A. Saady, A.I. Eatah and M.M. Masoud, DC pseudo plasma discharge treatment of polyester textile surface for disperse dyeing, *JOTI.* Vol. 97(2): 111-117, 2006.
- [18] Kh. El-Nagar, H.S. Suzan, A.S. Mohamed and A. Ramadan "Mechanical Properties and Stability to Light Exposure for Dyed Egyptian cotton Fabrics with Natural and Synthetic Dyes". *Polymer-Plastics Technology and Engineering.* Vol. 44: 1269-1279, 2005.
- [19] H. Barbara (2005) Infrared spectroscopy: fundamentals and application, John Wiley & Sons. Ltd., Southern Gate, Chichester, England.
- [20] ISO 4589: Determination of flammability by oxygen index (1984-12-15).
- [21] ISO 1210: Determination of the burning behavior of horizontal and vertical specimens in contact with small-flame ignition source (1992).
- [22] C. Marazzato, Y. Peneva, E. Lefterova, S. Filippi and L. Minkova "Kinetics of non-isothermal degradation of nanocomposites based on functionalized polyethylenes". *Polym. Test.* Vol. 26(4): 526-536, 2007.
- [23] W. Wu, H. Qu, Z. Li, H. Yu "Thermal behavior and flame retardancy of flexible poly(vinyl chloride) treated with zinc hydroxyl stannate and zinc stannate". *J Vinyl Addit. Technol.* Vol. 14: 10-15, 2008.
- [24] M. Talukdar and P.G.R. Achary "Sunthesis and Characterization of Some Controlled Structure Thermotropic Liquid Crystalline Polyesters". Synthesis & Characterization of Crystalline Polyester, *IJRRAS*, Vol. 3(2):132, 2010.
- [25] O. Abdel-Kareem and Kh. EL-Nagar "Non destructive Methods to investigate the deterioration extent of Coptic Egyptian textiles". *Journal of Textile and Apparel, Technology and Management.* Vol. 4(4): 1-15, 2005.
- [26] <http://www.lenntech.com/library/ozone/reaction/ozone-reaction-mechanisms.htm#ixzz1k1vbNC6f>
- [27] E.P.G. Gohl, L.D. Vilensky. Textile Science, CBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi. 1999.
- [28] S.F. Ibrahim, Kh. El-Nagar, F.M. Tera. (2012). "Improving Wool Printability at Reduced Energy

Using UV/Ozone Treatment". *RJTA*. Accepted for publication. 2012.

- [29] J.F. Rabek. 1995. *Polymer Photodegradation; Mechanisms and Experimental Methods*. Chapman and Hall. London 185–207 (Chapter 3).
- [30] R.S.C. Woo, Y. Chen, H. Zhu, J. Li, J.K. Kim and C.K.Y. Leung "Environmental degradation of epoxy–organoclay nanocomposites due to UV exposure". Part I: Photo-degradation. *Composites Science and Technology*. Vol. 67: 3448-3456, 2007.
- [31] M. N. Michael and N.A. El-Zaher. *Egypt. J. Chem.* Vol. 47: 93-100, 2004.
- [32] F.M. Tera, Kh. El-Nagar and S.M. Mohamed "Dyeability and light fastness properties of onion scale dye on different fabric types for conservation applications". *JTATM*, Vol. 7(3): 1-6, 2012.
- [33] L. Lili, M.W. Frey and K.J. Browning "Biodegradability Study on Cotton and Polyester Fabrics". *Journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics*. Vol. 5(4): 42-53, 2010.
- [34] Y. Marechal and H. Chanzy "The hydrogen bond network in Ibeta cellulose as observed by infrared spectrometry". *J. Mol. Struct.* Vol. 523:183-196, 2000.
- [35] J. Sugiyama, J. Persson and H. Chanzy "Combined infrared and electron diffraction study of the polymorphism of native celluloses". *Macromolecules* Vol. 24: 2461-2466, 1991.
- [36] M. Cazacu, S. Dragan and A. Vlad, (2003). Organic-inorganic polymer hybrids and porous materials obtained on their basis.
- [37] A.R. Horrocks. *An Introduction to the Burning Behaviour of Cellulosic Fibres*. J.S.D.C, Vol. 99: 191-197, 1983.
- [38] Z. Ping, S. Shuying, W. Bing, S. Kai and S. Gang "A study of pyrolysis and pyrolysis products of flame-retardant cotton fabrics by DSC, TGA and PY-GC-MS". *Text. Res. J.*, Vol. 57(3): 161-167, 1987.

Fig. 1. Limiting oxygen index instrument.

Fig. 2. Flam chamber (UL/94) instrument.

Fig. 3. Effect of UV/Ozone exposure time on the fabric weight of polyester fabric.

Fig. 4. Effect of UV/O₃ radiation on polymeric materials (PH) [29, 30].

Fig. 5. FTIR spectra of treated samples (AS 2P-4P) and un-treated one (AS-1P) after irradiating with UV/Ozone for different time periods.

Fig. 6. Thermogravimetric studies of un-treated and treated samples with phosphorylated sol-gel coating after exposing to UV/Ozone for different periods (P1 at zero min; P2 at 30 min; P3 at 90 min and P4 for 125 min).

Fig. 7. DSC curves for un-treated sample (AS-1P), coated sample after irradiation with UV/Ozone periods, AS-2P (30 min), AS-3P (90 min) and AS-4P (125 min).

Table 1. Effect of UV/Ozone exposure time on colour components, yellowness and whiteness values of polyester fabric.

Sample name	Exposed time /(min)	L	a	b	W	Y
AS-1P	0	92.19	-0.77	1.44	74.40	2.56
AS-2P	30	91.97	-0.80	1.79	72.22	3.25
AS-3P	90	91.20	-0.89	2.27	70.07	4.10
AS-4P	125	91.17	-0.71	2.91	65.10	5.56

L (lightness), a (red-green), b (yellow-blue), W (whiteness) and Y (yellowness).

Table 2. It has the Flammability results (reaction to small flame) which determined by LOI and UL/94.

Samples after treating with UV/Ozone for diff. times (min)	LOI (%)	UL/94 RB (mm min ⁻¹)	Classification of fabric
0	18	109	class-3
30	24	0	class-1
90	27	0	class-1
125	22	0	class-1

Table 3. Values of transition temperature and heat of fusion for un-treated and treated samples.

Samples Data	T_g	$T_{m.c}$	ΔH	T_m	ΔH_m	T_{d1}	ΔH_1	T_{d2}	ΔH_2
	/°C	/°C	/J g ⁻¹	/°C	/J g ⁻¹	/°C	/J g ⁻¹	/°C	/J g ⁻¹
AS-1P	77.95	--	--	260.02	-7.92	399.10	+7.13	440.47	-18.59
AS-2P	94.23	123.19	-6.62	262.09	-13.88	413.09	-25.46	607.41	+8.83
AS-3P	103.35	125.33	-5.17	262.50	-20.69	419.82	-23.50	618.81	+27.67
AS-4P	90.76	120.85	-4.73	262.01	-10.29	405.88	-13.39	603.29	+7.63

T_g is the glass-transition temperature, T_m is the melting temperature, $T_{m.c}$ is the melting temperature of the coated samples, ΔH is the heat of fusion, ΔH_m is the heat of fusion of melting temperature, T_{d1} is the temperature of the first decomposition, ΔH_1 is the first heat decomposition, T_{d2} is the temperature of the second decomposition and ΔH_2 is the second heat decomposition.